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BIO-MONITORING OF ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTANTS

Biomonitoraggio degli inquinanti ambientali

The INSIGNIA-EU project aims to design and test an innovative, non-invasive, scientifically proven citizen science environmental monitoring protocol for the detection of pesticides, microplastics, heavy metals and air pollutants by honey bee colonies. Honeybee colonies are excellent bio-samplers of biological material such as nectar, pollen and plant pathogens, as well as non-biological material such as pesticides or airborne contamination <http://insignia-eu.eu>. In the pilot INSIGNIA project (INSIGNIA-bee, 2018-2021), a protocol was developed and tested for citizen-science based monitoring of pesticides using honeybees. As part of the project, biweekly pollen and beebread samples, were obtained from sentinel apiaries over a range of European countries and landscapes. Innovative non-biological matrices were also tested: i) the “Beehold tube”, a tube lined with the generic absorbent polyethylene-glycol PEG, through which hive-entering bees are forced to pass, and ii) the “APIStrip” (Absorbing Pesticides In-hive Strips) with a specific pesticide absorbent which is hung between the bee combs. The samples were also analysed for botanical origin, using state of the art molecular techniques, and for residues of 273 agricultural pesticides and veterinary products, both authorized and unauthorized.

The data collected are used to develop and test a spatial modelling system aimed at predicting spatially-explicit pollen diversity and pesticide mixture exposure and risk at the apiary level, from basic landscape data. The system consists of model components for spatial and temporal pollen resource

distribution, application and environmental fate of pesticides, and honeybee landscape-scale pollen foraging, with a common underlying geo-data base containing European land-use and land-cover data (CORINE), the LUCAS database (landcover) supplemented with national data sets on agricultural and (semi-)natural habitats. It requires data on the use of agrochemicals and on the phenology and other characteristics of the crops and wild flowers constituting the main pollen resources (BRODSCHNEIDER *et al.*, 2020; VAN DER STEEN *et al.*, 2021)

Brief results of the INSIGNIA-bee pilot study showed that:

1. Pesticide test on pollen to determine how many of the pesticides are retained or do not decompose in the 2-3 days after pollen collection. The result was the fact that in the end 90% of pesticides do not break down very easily (e.g. when sent to the analysis laboratory).
2. The Beehold tubes proved to be very obstructive to the bees, and with the heat the white material inside was melting.
3. The analysis on the amount of DNA derived from the plants (necessary for the distinction and identification of the plant origin of plants), in the pollen, in the bee bread and in the tubes, revealed that the best material is the pollen which is collected more easily and with the smallest nuisance in the hive.
4. The number of pesticides found in all materials and the frequency with which pesticides appeared were higher in the Apistrips films, the innovative method to absorb the chemicals in the atmosphere.
5. The analysis of pesticide residues in bee bread and APISrips films showed that in Greece as in other countries the quantities of pesticides found were very small, but some of these chemicals were not approved by the EU.

After a call by the European Commission, the INSIGNIA-EU consortium was formed, and a new 2 years project was granted aiming to present a comprehensive pan-European environmental pollution monitoring study with honey bees. Human activity impacts the environment in many ways. One of the more problematic impact is pollution of the environment and the type and quantity of pollutants varies greatly in different environments (ASTOLFI *et al.*, 2021; COCHARD *et al.*, 2021; GRENIER *et al.*, 2021). Although pesticides used in agriculture, are a known hazard due to their biological activity, these compounds are not restricted to the field and pest organisms they are applied to. Other pollutants have even been less obvious because we have not been aware of their impact for many years. An example is air pollution that increased while our societies industrialized and is currently regarded the single largest environmental health risk in Europe (<https://www.eea.europa.eu/>). Unfortunately, other pollutants such as heavy metals, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons,

polychlorinated biphenyls, airborne particulate matter and micro-plastics have also reached our environment. Especially from the latter one knowledge is available from the aquatic environment while its spread into the terrestrial environment is largely unknown.

Beekeepers as citizen scientists have been proven to be effective at sampling, for example by using pollen traps to collect pollen, but are also able to collect other sample matrices, when robust sampling procedures are applied and are well explained (GRATZER & BRODSCHNEIDER, 2021). The outcome of the project will provide the first standardized EU-wide monitoring of environmental pollutants with honey bee colonies. This will be achieved by a network of beekeepers, sampling their own colonies as citizen scientists.

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